

Pressure- and Aggregation-Induced Modulation of Linear and Nonlinear Optical Properties in a Push-Pull Chromophore: Insights from Computational Modelling

input_absorption: example of a gaussian input file for a TD-DFT calculation of absorption properties at S0 geometry

input_nci: example input file for non-covalent interaction region computation performed with NCIPLOT programme

input_output_qe: example input and output file for crystal geometry optimization in Quantum ESPRESSO with periodic boundary conditions at P = 0 kbar

opti_0kbar_crystal: optimized geometry of unit cell at 0 kbar; .vasp and .cif file

opti_press_crystal: all optimized unit cell geometries from 1-30 kbar; .cif files

press_dimers_geom: all dimers extracted from optimized unit cell geometries from 1-30 kbar; .pdb files